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Executive Summary

This deliverable aims at getting the conversation about data protection, ethics and governance within HEAP going. A common instrument for assessing and addressing data protection requirements involves conducting a data protection impact assessment (DPIA). The purpose of this partial DPIA is to assess where in HEAP which possible threats should be considered, and to provide a roadmap for how to address these further over the coming period. It will be developed iteratively as the project develops. The deliverable builds on and supplements other documents and deliverables and should be read in conjunction with it, in particular the HEAP Data Management Plan (D7.1), the HEAP Reference Architecture (D10.1), and documentation of informed consents, consenting procedures and accessibility of cohort-wise data relating to HEAP data sources (D13.1).

The structure of this document follows the HEAP data life cycle and the various components of the HEAP Platform. For each component, the general status and questions which need to be addressed in developing HEAP in relation to legal terms of use are discussed. The list below provides a short summary.

Data sources

- In principle, it is assumed that each data custodian remains responsible for checking and allowing data use for a specific research project and whether such use is allowed. Legal terms of use per data source are summarised in a table in [section 4.1](#).
- Further details, including procedures, will need to be established in the HEAP data access governance.

The HEAP Platform

- According to the HEAP reference architecture, custody over the data in the IC will not be transferred. This means that CSC as host to the Platform will only serve as a data processor on behalf of HEAP and/or researchers making use of HEAP.
- Similarly, Logical Clocks and developers of the Hopsworks Platform will not be involved in the data processing on the Platform itself.
- Security measurements will need to be documented in more detail in a follow-up deliverable or DPIA and/or data management plan.

Submission engine

- Currently, responsibility relating to data minimisation and de-identification will reside with the data sources *prior* to submitting data into the submission engine. Whether this approach affords sufficient protections, or whether guidance or tooling is needed to address this and

what role the SE can play therein, is a point that will need to be taken up in discussions within the consortium.

- Necessity and proportionality must be demonstrated by the controller of the data, being the data source, also for submission to the HEAP IC.

Information Commons

- In principle, data can be made available on-demand through the IC in the KE) only for the purposes and time period of specific analyses, subject to data governance.
- However, retention periods and policies for data in the IC after submission will need to be established, also for data generated on the Platform, as well as for beyond the duration of HEAP.

Knowledge engine and access to the Information Commons

- The Researcher will not interact directly with the Information Commons as its role is to facilitate access to the data. The KE will enquire the REMS for what data to present to specific users.
- Researchers will be able to access data for analysis after approval of the HEAP Data Access Committee (DAC), subject to approval by the data source(s).
- Researchers are only provided access for analysis of data on the Platform itself. Data cannot be downloaded from the Platform.
- Access and use procedures of the HEAP DAC will be drawn up in the course of the Data Governance Framework (D2.3). One challenge there is how this approval procedure will (need to) relate to local approvals, and any per-project data protection measures that may be needed.

Data and feature warehouse

- The HEAP (meta)data and feature warehouse will not involve personal data per se. Possibly some basic controls need to be put in place for this. If the data warehouse is developed further into a broader data warehouse, further checks for anonymising data will be required.

Entitlements Management System

- The Entitlements Management system (EMS) is a technical tool facilitating data access and managing access rights. If the HEAP Platform is submitted to a complete DPIA, this system will also require assessment.

Controllership and processorship: distribution of responsibilities under data protection law

- The precise distribution of responsibilities for data processing in HEAP will require further specification.

- This relates to legal uncertainty with respect to the concept of controllership, but also to further clarification and decisions to be made over the organisation of and data governance in HEAP.

International Transfers

- Some data collected and shared in HEAP as part of the Finnish use cases involves explicit limitations with respect to territorial data transfers.
- More generally, data sharing beyond the European Economic Area is an issue for HEAP.
- A number of legal routes for resolving this situation exist, which will be assessed further.

Preliminary conclusions

- Necessity and proportionality will need to be justified for data to be uploaded by the data sources and data which to be retained after analysis.
- There is a legal basis for all cohorts to research on the data. It should be further assessed whether this also implies that others may have access to the data as joint controllers or that data may be transferred to them.
- More finetuning and legal research is needed about who are the (joint) controllers in HEAP data lifecycle.
- CSC as IC host serves as processor. There will be a need for controller-processor agreements before the first transfer of data to the IC.
- A radical approach to the challenges of a legal basis for data submission and use by researchers, is to consider the data in the KE anonymous from the perspective of the researchers working with this data. This position requires further elaboration.
- HEAP policies with respect to (limitations to) exercising data subjects' rights need to be established and publicised.
- This document has collected the basic (public) information about security standards that are met. A full DPIA of the HEAP Platform will need to establish the security standards and assurances in more depth.
- The metadata warehouse will contain "Open Data", meaning that everybody can access them. Mechanisms should be set in place to assure that the (meta)data and feature warehouse do not publish personal data. If the data warehouse is developed further into a broader data warehouse, such as an archive for 'open data', further checks for anonymising data will be required.

Further work

The above leads to a number of points which will need to be addressed in the course of developing HEAP. The table in [section 7](#) provides an overview of the points raised throughout this deliverable, and a specification of where these will be taken up.

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Definitions and abbreviations

The following definitions and abbreviations are used.

API	Application Programming Interface (1)
CSC	CSC – IT Center for Science
DAC	HEAP Data Access Committee
(Data) Controller	the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data (GDPR, article 4.7).
Data custodian	a person or an automated process implementing data access based on access grants on behalf of the data controller
(Data) Processor	a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of a controller (GDPR, article 4.8)
Data source	The source of data provided to HEAP, such as a cohort. Each data source has a data controller and a data custodian acting on behalf of that controller.
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment. See also GDPR, article 35
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load (2)
FAIR	The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (3)
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
HEAP	Human Exposome Assessment Platform (4)
IC	HEAP Information Commons
KE	HEAP Knowledge Engine
KI	Karolinska Institutet
Personal data	any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental,

	economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person (GDPR, article 4.8)
REMS	Resource Entitlement Management System
SSI	Statens Serum Institut

1 Introduction

The HEAP WP2 deliverables aim at addressing (compliance with) data protection requirements for HEAP. This deliverable aims at getting the conversation about data protection, ethics and governance within HEAP going. This should help guide the process of considering data protection architecture, governance and design choices, and technical and organisational measures that can and should be taken.

A common instrument for assessing and addressing data protection requirements involves conducting a data protection impact assessment (DPIA). A DPIA has the following essential purposes: to describe the planned data processing operations in a systematic way; to evaluate whether these processing operations are necessary and proportional in relation to the purposes; and to identify the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons arising from these data processing operations, as well as the measures that should be adopted in order to mitigate them to the extent that they become acceptable in the context considered. In short, a DPIA must assess whether the data processing complies with the requirements of necessity and proportionality, legal basis and protection of human subject rights. The DPIA must show that possible threats are minimised to an acceptable level.

The purpose of this partial DPIA is to assess where in HEAP which possible threats should be considered, and to provide a roadmap for how to address these further over the coming period. It will be developed iteratively as the project develops. The deliverable thereby serves a number of “meta” objectives:

- For work package 2: to lay the groundwork for the HEAP data governance framework (Deliverable 2.3);
- For HEAP: to help ensure compliance with data protection during the course of the project, by assessing where data protection issues need to be considered further in the design of the project (Task 2.1);
- For health research generally: to develop guidance on data protection and compliance for data-driven infrastructural platforms, set up for broadly defined, open-ended research purposes.

2 Scope of this deliverable

This document provides:

- An overview of the HEAP data life cycle from a data protection perspective;
- An overview of the legal grounds and distribution of responsibilities within HEAP from the perspective of data protection for HEAP as a whole;
- An overview of the main challenges and issues to be explored and addressed further in the course of HEAP from the perspective of data protection.

The structure of this document follows an adaptation of the DPIA templates of the French and UK data protection authorities (CNIL and ICO) (5,6). Adaptation was necessary as these templates relate to linear data processing: one data source, one purpose or a few very related purposes, one controller. In HEAP, as in many research projects, the situation is more complex.

The document was developed through a legal and ethical analysis and study of available HEAP documentation and discussions with HEAP partners and the WP7 work package on data management. The deliverable builds on and supplements other documents and deliverables and should be read in conjunction with it, in particular:

- The HEAP Data Management Plan (D7.1) (7)
- The HEAP Reference Architecture (D10.1) (8)
- Documentation of informed consents, consenting procedures and accessibility of cohort-wise data relating to HEAP data sources (D13.1).

The scope and approach to be followed in a potential subsequent DPIA will be informed in large part by the outcomes of this initial deliverable.

Aspects that will be addressed in any case later on (as set in deliverables):

- (Residual) risks and measures taken for the HEAP consumer receipts cohort, as well as other data and samples collected primarily for the purposes of HEAP (M24);
- Other elements of the HEAP data life cycle not already covered. This includes in particular elements relating to data protection that will be addressed in the HEAP data governance framework and the Knowledge Sharing component of the data life cycle (to be developed for the deliverable on data governance D2.3, due M48).

3 The HEAP data life cycle

The overall goal of HEAP is to enable global collaborative exposome research towards cost-effective health interventions. This will be provided by a platform enabling combination of i) advanced, joint information technology, ii) advanced exposome measurement technology and iii) uniquely large longitudinally followed population-based cohorts that will provide valuable actionable knowledge about women’s health and healthy child-bearing. Data will come from long established cohort studies, consumer recipes and sensors (see section 5).

HEAP data processing consists of a number of elements. Figure 1 provides a sketch of the data life cycle for HEAP as a whole. For the purposes of this deliverable, we distinguish in particular between the *data sources* on the one hand and the other components on the other hand, which together make up the *HEAP Platform*.

Figure 1: HEAP data life cycle (<https://heap-exposome.eu/about/technology/>)

3.1 Data sources

Data from a number of *data sources*, consisting of data of participants of a number of cohorts and studies in Denmark, Finland and Sweden, will serve as use cases for the HEAP platform. These data sources are heterogeneous and includes for example registry data, data collected in the course of previous research projects and currently running research projects, data derived from biological samples and wearable devices. Some of the data to be shared through HEAP will be collected in the course of (and funded through) HEAP. See further on for specification.

For each data source, the HEAP Data Management Plan provides the purpose and relation to the objectives of the project, and Data utility, to whom data will be useful during and after the project (7). The main

characteristics from the perspective of data protection will be summarized in a subsequent section.

3.2 The HEAP Platform

The HEAP platform consists of a number of components, summarised in the Reference architecture (8) (figure 2): the *submission engine*, the *information commons*, the *knowledge engine*, and the *metadata warehouse* (in figure 1 referred to as the *data and feature warehouse*). Access to data is controlled through an *entitlements management system*.

The Information Commons will be developed and provided by CSC. The Knowledge Engine will be developed and provided through the Hopsworks AI Platform. The Platform (with the exception of the submission engine) will be hosted by CSC. The platform is horizontally scalable with the possibility to add additional instances of each component when necessary, such as more storage or compute nodes. Other instances may eventually be implemented at other HEAP participant institutions.

3.2.1 Submission Engine

Data from the data sources will be submitted to the Information Commons (IC) via the Submission Engine (SE) by data custodians authorized by the data sources. A Data Custodian can utilise ETL jobs to remove identifiable information from the data, create subsets or any necessary jobs in order to make data available to the Information Commons. The Submission Engine will interface with the Information Commons via the Submission API, an API that facilitates storing sensitive data in an encrypted format.

The Submission Engine and API will be developed by WP10. Components developed by WP10 and WP6 will be interconnected to make it seamless to the user that the data uploaded via the SE will be available to Hopsworks. Hopsworks might be used to perform some of the ETL jobs required to anonymize and curate the data before submission.

3.2.2 Information Commons

The HEAP Information Commons (IC) is the data repository infrastructure that provides on-demand data accessibility and availability following the HEAP ethical and regulatory framework. It includes the physical resources to store and archive HEAP data and the interfaces to make this data available for analysis and future research.

The IC has the architecture of a vault with safety deposit boxes or private resources that only the data owner/data (custodians) of deposited data will have access and control over their respective datasets. In coordination with the custodians, the Data Access Controller/Committee (DAC) can provide means to facilitate data access via the Entitlements Management System component. The coordination of access approval between data custodians and DAC is an issue that will be taken up in the data governance framework (see below). The Researcher will not interact directly with the Information Commons (only through the Knowledge Engine, see below) as the role of the IC is only to facilitate access to the data.

The data can be processed on-demand in the IC. This implies that the data can remain at the respective data sources, and is provided to the IC only when required and on-demand processing for analysis in the Knowledge Engine. The data will be tailored to the analysis and can include pseudonymised data. However, the IC also aims at preserving data and information for current and future research as well as provide the compute infrastructure to support the Knowledge Engine component data processing needs.

3.2.3 Knowledge Engine

The system for data-driven analysis, bioinformatics and applied AI to data in the Information Commons to produce actionable knowledge. The KE and its general requirements are satisfied by the Hopsworks platform and will be developed by WP6.

The KE will interface directly with the Researcher providing the needed functionality to run analysis pipelines, compare sequence data, visualise results and even run machine learning pipelines by integrating with the feature store - see Requirements Matrix (chapter 4). An instance of Hopsworks can be installed in a Virtual Machine (see Figure 2).

3.2.4 Data and feature warehouse

The HEAP data and feature Warehouse acts as an online catalogue that makes metadata about the data stored in Information Commons and Knowledge Engine Data and Feature Store available to stakeholders and the general public. The current development focus is on two 'technical' parts of this warehouse: the Metadata Warehouse and the Feature Store.

The HEAP *Metadata Warehouse* will leverage repositories and metadata specifications in order to index data resources in a catalogue and make it available for access and use by researchers or other interested parties. WP7 is primarily responsible for the development of the metadata warehouse.

Hopsworks also provides a *Feature Store* to curate, store, and document features for use in ML pipelines. The feature store serves as the interface between data engineering and data science in HopsML pipelines and was designed with a focus on reuse/collaboration, versioning, automatic feature analysis etc. The Feature Store can also be understood as a component of the Knowledge Engine.

3.2.5 Entitlements management system

The *Entitlements Management system* is a tool that concentrates on two goals:

- *Facilitate* data access as security and rights management without making data access unnecessarily cumbersome;
- *Manage* access rights to resources and provide traceability of the data access rights granted.

Researchers can use federated user IDs to log in, fill in the data access application and agree to the dataset's terms of use. The EMS system then circulates the application to the Data Access Controller or designated

representative for approval. EMS also produces the necessary reports on the applications and the granted data access rights.

The EMS will be developed by WP10 and will be based on the CSC Resource Entitlement Management System (REMS), drawing on validated secure standards for access delegation such as EOSC Life Science AAI protocols, OAuth and OpenID Connect and GA4GH passports (9–11).

4 Clarifying legal terms of use

This section maps out the general status and questions which need to be addressed in developing HEAP in relation to legal terms of use. Some of the key issues to be addressed are:

- How are formal responsibilities for data processing distributed within HEAP?
- What are the legal grounds for processing data in the context of HEAP?
- How can necessity and proportionality of processing be assessed?

4.1 Data sources

Although each of the participating cohorts has expressed that data is available in principle for use in HEAP, the precise scope of allowed research purposes can differ.

The basic architecture of HEAP is that of a federated governance arrangement, in which data remains under the control of individual consortium partners. Data custodians connected to the data sources are tasked with providing access to (a subset of) data from that data source. A data custodian acts on behalf of the controller of the data source.

Researchers involved in the analysis of such data will also become controllers for the processing of data in HEAP for their respective research projects, possibly jointly with the controllers of data sources. This also goes for research data generated through work conducted in the course of the HEAP consortium. Thus, in the course of research conducted through HEAP, a wider circle of HEAP consortium members involved in use cases involving pilot projects can potentially become joint controllers.

In principle, it is assumed that each data custodian remains responsible for checking and allowing data use for a specific research project and whether such use is allowed under previously provided informed consent and ethics approval, and/or whether additional information, consent and/or ethics approval is necessary. Further details, including procedures, will need to be established in the HEAP data access governance.

The following table summarises the kinds of data and sources to be included in HEAP, the legal basis under which data is being made available, and the main legal and institutional conditions and restrictions that may apply. A more detailed overview can be found in the Data Management Plan (D7.1) and the overview of legal bases (D13.1).

Data source	Data Custodian	Personal or anonymous data?	Kinds of data	Genetic data?	Participants	Origins of data	Geographic restrictions?	Other restrictions?
Swedish Cervical screening cohort	KI, Joakim Dillner	Personal	Data derived from samples from healthy tissue, pre-neoplastic lesions and cancer; register data; exposome data; health data	Yes	Women enrolled in the Swedish national cervical screening programme	Data collected from samples taken in the organized cervical screening program in Stockholm region, national health registers, and quality register databases; in addition, legacy data from the National Cervical Screening Register data and National health registers at National Board of Health and Welfare	?	Informed consent conditional on new ethical permission from Swedish Ethics Agency; ethical permission for participation in HEAP and adding data on epigenome and metagenome (microbiome) already in place
Finnish Maternity cohort (FMC)	UOULU, Heljä-Marja Surcel; KI/FICAN-MID, Matti Lehtinen	personal	Health data; microbiomics data; epidemiological data	No (no approval for genetics research)	Women enrolled in the Finnish national prenatal screening programming	Finnish National prenatal screening, with additional FMC screening results	Finland	Access approval through Findata
Finnish HPV Vaccination cohort (F-Vac)	KI/FICAN-MID, Ville Pimenoff and Matti Lehtinen	personal	Baseline health and follow-up STD data (cytology, HPV, chlamydia) from 60.000 participants; a subset from up to 50 HPV and chlamydia types x 60.000 participants x (5 to 10) for microbiome	No (no approval for genetics research)	Research participants: healthy volunteers, women	Community-randomized HPV vaccination and cervical screening trials; follow-up with additional STD follow-up results (cytology, HPV and	Finland	Access approval through FINGENIOUS

			metagenomics data			chlamydia) available		
HEAP consumer cohort	SSI, Frederik Trier Møller – potentially also other custodians	Personal	Consumer purchase data; scientific reports; data from registers and other research projects	No	Consumers	Commercial digital receipt providers (such as start-up company Storebox) and if possible, loyalty programmes (such as COOP, pending approval). The data is re-used from other sources such as Danish registers, quality databases, or research projects, as well as digital receipt solutions and loyalty programs	EU	Access approval potentially on a case-by-case basis; participants have possibility to opt out of specific studies; national ethics approval not needed for register research, only for research involving human material (currently not foreseen)
Wearable data collection study	KI, Michael Snyder; KI/FICAN-Mid, Matti Lehtinen; OU, Heljä-Marja Surcel	Personal	Environmental exposure data collected through wearable sensors, including: geolocation data, microbiomics sequencing data, metabolomics analysis data	No	Research participants: pregnant women, sub-cohort of F-Vac	Pilot study/trial	Finland	Access approval through FINGENIOUS

4.2 The HEAP Platform

The HEAP Platform facilitates research conducted by HEAP consortium partners involved in the use cases, and eventually other researchers as well.

According to the HEAP reference architecture, custody over the data in the IC will not be transferred. This means that CSC as host to the Platform will only serve as a data processor on behalf of HEAP and/or researchers making use of HEAP. CSC does not assume ownership or custody over the data it handles. Similarly, Logical Clocks and other developers of the Hopsworks Platform will not be involved in the data processing for research purposes on the Platform itself.

Note that the legal role of a data processor comes with a strict delineation of legal responsibilities: institutions hosting the IC and/or KE should in such cases not make any decisions as to purposes for which the data will be used, and should only provide the means for the HEAP research as approved by the data controllers.

These delineations may be of importance if the HEAP Platform does not only have a federated governance but also a federated infrastructure meaning that not all data processing activities for the research will be executed at CSC. This would mean that IC hosts would only be allowed to serve as data custodians or gain access for research for those data of which they are the controllers/custodians already or if additional conditions are being met comparable to the conditions CSC is subject to. This means a strict distinction between the roles of a processor and that of a researcher. There should be “Chinese walls” between the two functions, meaning distinct databases with distinct access roles and oversight. The legal issue, including some potential arrangements and additional measures involved can be clarified further in a future deliverable if needed.

The HEAP platform will be developed on the basis of the Hopsworks platform by Logical Clocks AB. The Platform will be deployed on the CSC-developed ePouta private cloud service (12). Specific technical and organisational measures for data protection, including security measures, depend in large part on how ePouta and Hopsworks will be configured. CSC’s information security management systems are certified according to ISO/IEC 27001 standards (13).¹ A number of guidelines for safe and secure use have been

¹ TBD whether other assurances such as ISAE 3402 are or should be in place.

developed as well (14). A generic DPIA on ePouta has not been conducted as of yet. Hopsworks' security model includes a.o. dynamic role-based access control as well as encryption of data both in transit and at-rest (15). Security measurements will need to be documented in more detail in a follow-up deliverable or DPIA and/or data management plan.

A number of specific points relating to various platform components are discussed below.

4.2.1 *Submission engine*

As part of its participation in HEAP, each data source will use the Submission Engine in order to make data available in/through the Information Commons.

Our understanding is that any responsibility relating to data minimisation and de-identification (pseudonymisation or anonymisation) is currently outside the scope of the HEAP consortium and will reside with the data sources *prior* to submitting data into the submission engine, and will thus reside with the individual controllers (i.e. not with the HEAP consortium as a whole). Whether this approach affords sufficient protections, or whether guidance or tooling is needed to address this and what role the SE can play therein, is a point that will need to be taken up in discussions within the consortium.

At the very least, necessity and proportionality (i.e. with respect to the amount and level of detail of data being shared through HEAP) must be demonstrated by the controller of the data, being the data source, also for submission to the HEAP IC. A mere 'dump' of all their data simply because they might in the future be used for HEAP research is by itself insufficient for this demonstration. It could only be justified if all data are needed for a more concrete research question which is at least concretely foreseeable. It is to be discussed whether reiterative searching the source databases for more refined research questions and only filling the IC with the results of those searches, is doable for the source data and if not, that could be a justification for filling the IC with more data. This should also be discussed in a new round of this DPIA.

4.2.2 *Information Commons*

The IC facilitates data access and availability. In principle, data can be made available on-demand in the IC (meaning: through the IC in the KE) only for the purposes and time period of specific analyses, subject to data governance (see further on). However, retention periods and policies for

data in the IC after submission will need to be established. Moreover, archiving and retention periods and policies for data generated on the Platform will need to be established in the course of the project as well, also for beyond the duration of HEAP. (It is understood that CSC's role is focused primarily on catering to (data stewardship for) Finnish research.)

Genomic data will be stored and analysed in encrypted form using Crypt4GH. Crypt4GH makes it possible to efficiently keep data (and index) files in an encrypted state that is directly accessible by current tools for analysis without the need to create a decrypted copy (16). Crypt4GH can be used for any data format. It should be established whether it will be applied across the board on all data – and if not, whether and what other standards will be used for other kinds of data. The standard will likely at least be used for data which is as sensitive as genomic data in terms of personal identifiability, such as epigenetic data.

4.2.3 Knowledge engine and access to the Information Commons

The *Researcher* will not interact directly with the Information Commons as its role is to facilitate access to the data. Access to data will be provided through a CSC provided client (FUSE layer) that will only show the user the data that it currently has access to. The KE (Hopsworks) will enquire the REMS for what data to present to specific users.

Researchers will eventually be able to gain access to data for analysis after approval of the HEAP Data Access Committee (DAC), subject to approval by the data source(s). Researchers are only provided access for analysis of data on the Platform itself. Data cannot be downloaded from the Platform.

Access and use procedures of the HEAP DAC will be drawn up in the course of the Data Governance Framework (D2.3). One challenge that needs to be tackled there is how this approval procedure will (need to) relate to local institutional and ethics approvals, and any per-project data protection measures that may need to be put in place. A two-tiered procedure would be feasible:

- A decision by the HEAP DAC, together with
- A decision by each of the data sources whose data will be used in a project, following its own applicable rules for allowing research with the data (such as approval by an ethics committee).

Questions that can then be raised are which comes first, whether some approvals can be delegated to the HEAP DAC entirely, and to what extent access approval for researchers affiliated with the HEAP consortium is already covered by the HEAP consortium agreement. The aim should be to aim for an efficient approval procedure that can flexibly accommodate new

data sources and researchers that are not yet members of the HEAP consortium eventually.

If the HEAP DAC shapes which research may be executed using the HEAP Platform, it might also become a joint controller, together with the data sources and the researcher which requests access. In our opinion, such a role should be avoided. An additional argument for a limited role would be that a larger role would necessitate the research projects to be vetted twice, at the data source and by the DAC. In a future discussion the role of the DAC should be delineated further. One could think of mere scientific advice whether the research can be executed using the HEAP Platform or a slightly larger role.

Other aspects to consider in data access governance procedures are:

- How FAIR data stewardship can be combined with protection of data subjects' rights;
- Specific arrangements relating to role-based access control for researchers and data custodians (and possibly other types of users of the platform);
- Licensing terms on data and results generated through the platform, also in light of the FAIR principles;
- Potential data protection concerns over additional software and code deployed by researchers on the HEAP platform;
- Submission and publication requirements emerging from HEAP-facilitated journal publications

4.2.4 Data and feature warehouse

The HEAP data and feature warehouse consists of a metadata catalogue on the one hand (a catalogue of data resources available in/through HEAP) and a Feature store for facilitating machine learning. In our understanding, neither aspect should involve personal data per se. However, at least for the metadata catalogue this may be something for which some basic controls need to be put in place (e.g. for checking and/or safeguarding anonymity). In addition, a mapping of DOI metadata terms onto GDPR terms will be considered. Finally, it should be considered whether and how legal terms of use of data sources should also be coded into metadata, for instance by drawing on the GA4GH Data Use Ontology (17).

If the data warehouse is developed further into a broader data warehouse, such as an archive for 'open data' or a public knowledge base for exposome research, further checks for anonymising data will be required.

4.2.5 Entitlements Management System

The Entitlements Management system (EMS) is a technical tool facilitating data access and managing access rights. This will be developed by WP10, likely based on the CSC Resource Entitlement Management System (REMS) and validated secure standards for access delegation such as EOSC Life Science AAI protocols, OAuth and OpenID Connect, and GA4GH passports. If the HEAP Platform is submitted to a complete DPIA, this system will also require assessment.

4.3 **Controllership and processorship: distribution of responsibilities under data protection law**

The precise distribution of responsibilities for data processing in HEAP will require further specification. This relates to legal uncertainty with respect to how controllership operates in complex research collaborations, but also to further clarification and decisions to be made over data governance in HEAP.

The basic architecture of HEAP is that of a *federated governance arrangement*, in which data remains under the control of individual partners' data sources.

- Access to a data source is mediated by a data custodian. The custodian decides whether access may be given for a specific research project. Access will then be provided through the Knowledge Engine. It remains to be discussed whether the researcher should mention all those to whom access should be given for the approved research in the application or whether this can be done at a later stage and will be implemented in the Platform. The data custodian is the controller of the data source (or tasked by the controller), in the sense of the GDPR of the data that data source originally keeps.
- A *Researcher* making use of such data through HEAP. From a legal point of view this means a transfer of the data from the custodian to the researcher or a common research project where researcher and custodian will become joint controllers.
- This question also applies to the further life cycle of the data. During the lifecycle of HEAP data processing this original data custodian remains the sole controller of the data, becomes joint controller together with others, such as the researchers which will use the data, or ceases to be controller of the data and instead submits data to a third party. In the latter case that third party will become the new controller or joint controller, together with other parties. If the intention is that the original data controllers are to remain controllers for the personal data during the HEAP lifecycle, this will have consequences for the data governance. In that case, they should approve each project which will make use of 'their'

data also in the case when they are derived data, in the sense of the results of analyses of the original data.

- Currently, the core of the HEAP Platform will consist of a single instance, hosted by CSC. Adding other platform components are also added at other institutions (e.g. additional storage and/or compute nodes) will require adjustment of data processing arrangements involved.
- The HEAP platform itself (more precisely, the platform's instance(s) involved therein), serve as *processor* on behalf of these controllers. The situation of CSC is clear, namely a processor, but that of the other partners is less clear. The HEAP consortium itself in shaping and co-determining purposes and means might be considered joint controllers, especially if the DAC is given a large role. The choice of arrangement depends very much on the mission of HEAP. The data governance framework in this respect should formalise this mission.

5 International Transfers

Finnish law, or Finnish research ethics committees, prohibits the transfer of personal data and biosamples of Finnish cohorts beyond Finnish jurisdiction. We understand this as a requirement that the data must *reside* in Finland. Otherwise non-Finnish researchers could never be given access.²

Data sharing beyond the European Economic Area (the territorial scope of the GDPR) adds a further dimension to this. Roughly summarised, EU data protection law only allows data sharing beyond EU jurisdictions provided that additional safeguards are met.³ This is a point of attention for HEAP, as one of the use cases involves partners that are (partly) based in the United States. Moreover, data collected in the course of the wearable pilot study may require processing by third parties based in countries beyond EU jurisdiction. In addition, allowing access to the HEAP platform to researchers in the United States data could be considered a form of international data transfer, even if the data itself does not leave the platform.

A number of legal routes for resolving this situation exist, which will be assessed further:

- A legal arrangement between HEAP data controllers and US-based partners is possible in principle. Such an arrangement would involve the use of the European Commission's Standard Contractual Clauses,

² Formally, online access even without the ability to download the data as a controller could be considered a form of cross-border processing already.

³ The situation is easier for jurisdictions for which the European Commission has taken a so-called adequacy decision, such as Switzerland and Japan. Data sharing with those jurisdictions is legally treated in the same way as data sharing within Europe. An adequacy decision for the United Kingdom is currently in preparation. An adequacy decision for the United States does not exist and is not expected in the foreseeable future.

combined with technical and organisational measures to ensure compliance with the EU level of data protection as set out by the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) (18). Some of the measures mentioned by EDPB may be achievable for HEAP. In principle, the EDPB considers effective pseudonymisation with some additional safeguards to prevent re-identification after transfer an effective measure. This option would be available, provided that (a) the parties involved (both data custodian and US partner) are willing and able to engage in such a contractual arrangement, (b) supplementary measures are workable, and (c) ethics approval allows for this.

- Alternatively, participants could be asked to explicitly consent to their data being transferred to a third country where potentially lower legal safeguards apply. This option crucially relies on ethics approval as well.
- If neither of these options would be available, different arrangements for processing data in the EU or under Finnish jurisdiction may need to be sought, with US partners only being allowed access through another EU-based research institution.
- As a last recourse, The GDPR also allows for non-repetitive transfers of data from a limited number of data subjects under certain conditions.

6 Preliminary conclusions

Necessity and proportionality

Data sources will need to justify why which data are uploaded to the HEAP IC in context of necessity and proportionality. As discussed, this could in principle the case yet more work is needed to set the criteria when and how that is actually the case.

Necessity and proportionality must also be justified for those data which will be retained after the analyses are done. In principle the justification could be that the results of the analyses must be controllable and in principle be reproducible. Yet, if these data would be kept on the same level of IC, the IC would grow far beyond the necessity and proportionality for a specific research project. A separate solution must be found for this such as 'containers' of the original data of each analysis, which can only be opened up under special circumstances.

Legal basis

There is a legal basis for all cohorts to research on the data, being the original consent of the participants, in some cases combined with a legal basis in national law. It should be further assessed whether this consent also implies that others may have access to the data as joint controllers or that the data may be transferred to them. The alternative would be that

there is an additional legal basis based on the national law of the cohort for this further processing without consent in the sense of the GDPR being the legal basis.

It might be argued that this aspect is outside scope of the HEAP DPIA as each cohort will control that itself before granting access. Yet, the researcher which has been granted access, will need a legal basis as well. In the case of joint controllers, it might be argued that the researcher can then build on the legal basis of the original controller. It should be mentioned that this argument has not been explicitly made in the discussion on research data and is open to challenges. If the argument does not hold or in any case when the data are transferred to the new researcher, this researcher will also require a legal basis for processing data.

Of course, this problem does not arise if the original controller/data source is the only entity which does research on the data, using the HEAP Platform research pipeline. More finetuning but also legal research is needed about who are the (joint) controllers in HEAP data lifecycle.

As seen, CSC is a processor. There will be a need for a controller-processor agreement before the first actual transfer of data to the IC at CSC.

A radical approach to the challenges of a legal basis to submit the cohort data for other researcher and that of the researchers which will be granted access, is to consider the data in the KE anonymous from the perspective of the researchers working with this data. Provided that a number of criteria are met ('the six safes model' (19)), this could in principle be the case; but this position requires further elaboration.

Protection of data subjects' rights

The GDPR grants the data subject a number of rights. The rights can be limited in the context of research, yet this will very much depend on national law.⁴

Basically, these rights must be executed at the level of original cohort and in that sense are outside the scope of the HEAP platform.

But if there are new controllers, those must implement the rights as well. It is assumed here that already the level of the IC, there will only be pseudonymised data. Article 11 GDPR exempts a data controller from implementing the data subject rights if the data are pseudonymised.⁵ Any queries from data subjects about which data are on the HEAP Platform should then be referred back to the cohorts.

There should a clear policy about this. The HEAP site would be one of the places to notify this policy.

⁴ See the overview of MedLawconsult/MLC Foundation at : <https://www.medlaw.nl/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/GDPRrsh exemptionsv.1.4.pdf>

⁵ Discussion exception and how that is extremely unlikely

In this context also, the potential transfer to countries outside the EU/EEA or countries without an adequacy decision.⁶

Data security

CSC has been selected for its capacity to implement the research pipelines, its security policies and additionally that without this Finnish partner the valuable Finnish data cannot be used. This document has collected the basic (public) information about security standards that are met. A full DPIA of the HEAP Platform will need to establish the security standards and assurances in more depth.

The metadata warehouse will contain “Open Data”, meaning that everybody can access them. Mechanisms should be set in place to assure that these data are truly anonymous hence cannot be reidentified by anyone. If the data warehouse is developed further into a broader data warehouse, such as an archive for ‘open data’, further checks for anonymising data will be required.

7 Further work

The above leads to a number of points which will need to be addressed in the course of developing HEAP.

We could make a distinction here between:

- a. Issues to be addressed at the level of data sources, especially for those cohorts which were not created with HEAP in mind;
- b. Issues about the data subjects’ rights;
- c. Issues to be addressed at the security level;
- d. Issues to be addressed at the governance level of HEAP, such as who are controllers and the legal bases for researchers.

The table below provides an overview of the points raised throughout this deliverable, and a specification of where these will be taken up.

Challenge	To be taken up by	When
Settle responsibilities of HEAP data custodians for terms of data use in sufficient detail and in a data access procedure	WP2: Data Governance Framework (D2.3)	M48 or before data processing on the Platform

⁶ Meaning that EU has taken a formal decision that

Document and assess security (including encryption) standards and assurances for all different kinds of data, including REMS	In a follow-up data management plan (WP7) and DPIA (WP2)	TBD
Assess and clarify responsibility and technical measures for ensuring necessity and proportionality of data processing in HEAP: e.g. de-identification, data minimisation measures	WP2 through WP7 (DMP) and WP10 (SE)	Relatively short term, TBD with WP7 and WP10
Clarify approach and policies for data retention on the IC: after submission; for the purposes of specific analyses; for data generated on the Platform; during and beyond the HEAP consortium	WP7 (DMP) and WP10 (IC), assisted by WP2, will be incorporated in Data Governance Framework (D2.3)	TBD
Access and use procedures of the HEAP Data Access Committee (DAC): relationship to approval procedures of individual data sources; per-project and generic approvals; eventual accommodation of data sources and researchers not part of the HEAP consortium	WP2: Data Governance Framework (D2.3)	M48 or before data processing on the Platform
Other aspects of data governance to be tackled: e.g. combining FAIR data stewardship with protection of data subjects' rights; detailed arrangements for role-based access control pf	WP2: Data Governance Framework (D2.3), together with WP7	M48 or before data processing on the Platform

researchers and data custodians; licensing terms on data and results generated through the platform, also in light of the FAIR principles; data protection of software and code deployed by researchers on the HEAP platform; submission and publication requirements emerging from HEAP-facilitated journal publications		
Data protection / anonymisation policies and measures for the metadata catalogue, feature store and possible other functions of the warehouse	WP7 (metadata warehouse), assisted by WP2	TBD
Mapping DOI metadata terms onto GDPR terms & v.v.	WP7-WP2 interaction	Short term
Coding data use terms into metadata: whether and how	WP7 (metadata warehouse), assisted by WP2	TBD
Further develop the mission of the HEAP platform for the purpose of data governance	HEAP consortium together with WP2, others	Relatively short term
Clarify data controllership status for HEAP consortium members; devise a suitable controller-processor framework agreement for HEAP	WP2: Data Governance Framework (D2.3)	M48 or before data processing on the Platform
Adjusting legal and governance arrangements if other instances of	WP2 on behalf of the HEAP consortium	TBD depending on developments in HEAP

platform components are added at other institutions		
Clarify and assess the possibilities and conditions for international data transfer in HEAP beyond EEA	WP2 together with use cases; to be included eventually in Data Governance Framework (D2.3)	Short term
Data subjects' rights policy for the HEAP Platform	WP2: Data Governance Framework (D2.3)	M48 or before data processing on the Platform

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